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TOURISM TEXTS AND THEIR PRAGMALINGUISTIC FEATURES

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ANNOTATION

This study is devoted to the creation and analysis of a communicative-pragmatic model of the presentation text of a tourism destination. The presentation text is at the center of social communication; therefore, it is of interest to create universal linguistic models within the framework of the theory and style of the text. This article is complex in nature, due to the specifics of the studied material, which combines the features of advertising, tourism discourse. According to the views of linguistics, it is fundamental to study the linguistic embodiment of strategies for speech impact on the target audience, the communicative context, which is formed from several sub contexts.

The work is due to the increasing attention to research carried out within the framework of the communicative-pragmatic paradigm of knowledge. It is extremely important in the work to address the communicative-pragmatic aspects of the language. This approach to the study of presentation text allows us to comprehensively describe the model of the text and characterize its elements. In addition, linguistic modeling is globally associated with the systematization of humanitarian knowledge, its modernization into precisely defined concepts and structures.

Key words: Social communication, linguistic models, communicative-pragmatic model, pragmalinguistic features, materials on tourism, pragmatically directed linguistics.

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TURIZM MATNLARI VA ULARNING PRAGMALINGVISTIK XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu tadqiqot turizm hududlarining taqdimot matnining kommunikativ-pragmatik modelini yaratish va tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan. Taqdimot matni ijtimoiy muloqot markazida; shuning uchun ham matn nazariyasi va uslubi doirasida universal lingvistik modellarni yaratish qiziqish uyg'otadi. Ushbu maqola o'rganilayotgan materialning o'ziga xos xususiyatlariga ko'ra murakkab xarakterga ega bo'lib, unda reklama, turizm nutqining xususiyatlarini birlashtiradi. Tilshunoslik nuqtai nazariga ko'ra, maqsadli auditoriyaga nutqning ta'sir qilish strategiyalarining lingvistik timsolini, bir nechta kichik matnlardan tashkil topgan kommunikativ kontekstni o'rganish muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Mazkur ish kommunikativ-pragmatik paradigma doirasida olib borilayotgan tadqiqotlarga e'tiborini qaratgani bilan ajralib turadi. Ishda tilning kommunikativ-pragmatik tomonlarini hal etish nihoyatda muhim. Taqdimot matnini o'rganishga bunday yondashuv matn modelini har tomonlama tavsiflash va uning elementlarini tavsiflash imkonini beradi. Bundan tashqari, lingvistik modellashtirish global miqyosda gumanitar bilimlarni tizimlashtirish, uni aniq belgilangan tushunchalar va tuzilmalarga modernizatsiya qilish bilan bog'liq.

Kalit so'zlar: Ijtimoiy muloqot, lingvistik modellar, kommunikativ-pragmatik model, pragmalingvistik xususiyatlar, turizmga oid materiallar, pragmatik yo'naltirilgan tilshunoslik.

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ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ТЕКСТЫ И ИХ ПРАГМАЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данное исследование посвящено созданию и анализу коммуникативно-прагматической модели текста презентации туристической дестинации. Текст презентации находится в центре социальной коммуникации; поэтому представляет интерес создание универсальных языковых моделей в рамках теории и стиля текста. Данная статья носит комплексный характер, что обусловлено спецификой изучаемого материала, сочетающего в себе черты рекламного, туристического дискурса. Согласно взглядам лингвистов, принципиальное значение имеет изучение языкового воплощения стратегий речевого воздействия на целевую аудиторию, коммуникативного контекста, который формируется из нескольких подконтекстов.

Работа обусловлена возрастающим вниманием к исследованиям, проводимым в рамках коммуникативно-прагматической парадигмы познания. Крайне важно в работе обращаться к коммуникативно-прагматическим аспектам языка. Такой подход к изучению презентационного текста позволяет всесторонне описать модель текста и охарактеризовать его элементы. Кроме того, лингвистическое моделирование глобально связано с систематизацией гуманитарного знания, его модернизацией в четко определенные понятия и структуры.

Ключевые слова: Социальная коммуникация, лингвистические модели, коммуникативно-прагматическая модель, прагмалингвистические особенности, материалы по туризму, прагматически направленная лингвистика.

“True overcoming of traditional ideas about language and the implicit semiotics hidden in them becomes possible in the light of the recognition of the fact that language can be understood in terms of behavior and action, i.e. Not as a ghostly sphere of information transmission hovering outside reality, but as a real element of the impact of reality itself. Language is not only a means of acquiring and transmitting knowledge, but also the objectification of knowledge that occurs in its peculiar structure, and, moreover, a certain life form. Who knows how to use language, he uses a certain strategy of orientation in the world, a certain interpretation of the human environment, a certain pattern of behavior? (Kelemen, 1977:106)

It can be assumed that, knowing the language, a person simultaneously knows a special - discursive - way of forming his relationship with reality. Those principles that provide this ability should be the object of the closest attention of linguists, although they are hidden from direct observation. Most likely, the area of their most distinct manifestation is the syntax of discourse, linking linguistic semantics (reflection of reality) with linguistic pragmatics (regulation of human relations with the environment).

Touristic text is persuasive: in the process of communication we are considering, an attempt is made to influence the addressee in order to get him to make a decision about the need, desirability, opportunity to go on a trip / visit a particular tourism object. To convince the addressee, the addresser

of the touristic text turns to different methods of influence, the dominant of which is speech. In touristic text, it is the focus of speech on the achievement of non-speech goals. Thus, through speech, the behavior of the addressee is regulated.

The persuasion of the touristic text addressee by means of verbal means includes the impact on the consciousness by appealing to the mind and the impact on the consciousness through the emotional sphere. According to the communicative approach, the rational-logical and persuasive ways of verbal persuasion are considered as argumentation that has a two-sided character: showing the truth (plausibility) of the thesis and creating an emotional attitude to the thesis, contributing to the perception of this thesis as a guide to action.

In order to prove a thesis or an enthymeme, the touristic text addresser uses various kinds of arguments and *topoi*. Argumentation in touristic text, which includes logical argumentation (which has a strong and lasting effect on the mind and behavior of the addressee) and rhetorical argumentation (which enhances the persuasiveness of speech), has a significant impact on the addressee.

Mass media texts are diverse and require scientific understanding [Vorob'eva, 2006]. In modern professional communication, information and advertising materials are widely used. One of them is the presentation text of the tourist destination. The specificity of this study is due to the diversity of terminology, which is largely determined by the material (presentation texts of the health tourism destination) and the subject of the work (communicative-pragmatic model). In this regard, there is a need to clarify the terminological apparatus, which is actively used in this study, and to identify the general principles of work aimed at effectively combining the linguistic, sociocultural and medical-valeological aspects of the study of communicative messages.

The word "destination" is consonant with the English destination, which translates as 1) destination and 2) destination, originally the word destination comes from the Latin "location" [English Russian dictionary, 1983, p. 656].

Analyzing the scope of the term "destination" in English, it should be noted that it has a spatial and territorial meaning. Destination is understood as a certain place, territory, towards which movement is carried out, i.e. The term "destination" is not narrowly specialized, it is used not only in the field of tourism. For example, in the oxford English dictionary, destination is defined as "the place to which a person or thing is going", i.e. A place where people currently go [Concise Oxford English dictionary, 2014, p.345]. With regard to the temporal characteristic of the definition, the movement action is considered as occurring at a given point in time (present continues).

The term "tourist destination" was introduced by n. Leiper, a professor at Meissen university (New Zealand) in 1973, who substantiated the first visual model of a tourism system and determined the place of a tourist destination in it [leiper, 1973]. Subsequently, this concept was repeatedly refined by foreign and domestic scientific schools.

The term of tourism practice "destination" is presented in the dictionary "dictionary of travel tourism and hospitality", which says that these are countries, regions, cities visited by tourists. Some domestic scientists adhere to a similar point of view [Goncharova, 2010].

The term "tourist destination" is interpreted as a place, visiting which leaves tourists with different impressions, experiences and emotions [Pearce, 1989], or as a motive for the trip [Cooper, 1993].

In the works of domestic scientists (M. B. Birzhakov, N. A. Goncharova, I. V. Zorin, M. A. Morozov, S. S. Nikolaev, E. N. Pavlova, A. A. Ryabtsev) under the tourist destination a geographic area that has a certain attractiveness for tourists. At the same time, it is specified that attractiveness may be different for different groups of tourists [Morozov, 1998].

In the works of some researchers, a tourist destination is presented in the sense of "a socio-geographical area that a tourist or a whole segment of consumers has chosen as the purpose of the trip and which has

Necessary institutions, organizations, accommodation facilities, services and infrastructure" [Nikolaev, 2000, p. 65].

In later sources, the semantics of the term is expanded and supplemented with new characteristics: "a tourist destination is a physical space in which a visitor spends time, including tourist services, attractions and tourist resources within one day of travel, having physical and administrative boundaries" [Zorin, 2005].

Significant for determining the content of the concept of "tourist destination" is the interpretation, where a tourist destination is understood as a multicomponent component of a tourist trip that characterizes its geographical, socio-cultural, regional, ethnographic and service values [Pavlova, 2010].

A tourist destination is considered as a center (territory of the state) with all kinds of amenities, facilities and services to meet the needs of tourists [Birzhakov, 2011].

Reflecting on the content of the term "tourist destination", the polish scientist J. Kaczmarek includes in the content of this concept a territory with structural tourist resources that form the tourist attractiveness of the destination [Kaczmarek, 2010]. J. Kaczmarek refers to the structural tourist resources of any territory as sights, tourist infrastructure, and transport accessibility.

Thus, in addition to definitional synonyms with the semantics of "territory", definitions of the term "destination" include the following professionalisms: travel motives, sights, tourist infrastructure, transport accessibility. Let's define some professional concepts necessary for the analysis of presentation texts of a tourist destination.

A tourist attraction is everything that may be of direct interest to a tourist and is an influential factor in choosing a tourist destination.

The following points of interest stand out in the scientific literature:

- natural - elements resulting from natural processes: mountains, caves, seas, lakes, forests, climatic conditions, health factors - mineral waters, thermal springs, therapeutic mud, salt caves;
- anthropogenic - sights created by people: religious shrines, castles, palaces, museums, galleries, landscape parks.

Tourism infrastructure covers those elements that ensure the normal functioning of the place of stay, subject to the maximum satisfaction of the needs of tourists. Tourist attractions are supported or supplemented by elements of tourist infrastructure (tourist trails, swimming pools, sports facilities, hotels of original architecture, etc.). The most important components of this infrastructure are:

- accommodation base - hotels and other accommodation facilities, sanatoriums, camp sites, guest rooms and other collective accommodation facilities;
- gastronomic base - all food outlets, both independent and located in accommodation facilities (snack bars, bars, pubs, restaurants, cafes, tea houses, pizzerias, canteens);
- accompanying base - devices and structures, the main purpose of which is to serve tourists: swimming pools, baths, sports equipment rental points, observation platforms, pump rooms;
- para-tourist base - facilities designed to meet other socio-economic needs, which J. Kaczmarek includes shops, cinemas, concert halls, theaters, Post offices, banks, libraries.

Transport accessibility implies the ability not only to reach the area that is the purpose of the trip, but also to move around it. Transport accessibility according to the classification of J. Kaczmarek is divided into:

- external accessibility, which is determined by the existing transport communication network between the place of residence of the tourist and the purpose of his trip (tourist destination);
- on internal accessibility, which is determined by the system of transport communications, tourist routes, the presence of which in the selected tourist destination allows the tourist to take walks to specific objects.

The structural resources indicated by J. Kaczmarek are extremely important for understanding the essence of a tourist destination.

In professional literature, several types of tourist destinations are distinguished: modern significant urban agglomerations, as well as state capitals and other major centers of business and cultural activity; ethnocultural centers where local customs and national culture are developed; specially created recreation and leisure centers. These are cities or settlements with natural or

artificially created attractions. This type includes recreational, balneological, health resorts and entertainment centers [Gergishan, 2011].

The definition proposed by the world tourism organization should be recognized as the most authoritative definition of a tourist destination: "the main destination of a tourism trip is defined as the place visited that is central to the decision to take the trip", i.e. The main destination is defined as the place visited at the basis of the decision to make the trip [official website of the world tourism organization].

Thus, a tourist destination in the dissertation is understood as a geographical area that has a certain attractiveness for a tourist in accordance with the motive of his trip, has structural resources, including places of interest, transport accessibility, accommodation facilities, catering, socio-cultural, regional-ethnographic and service values to meet customer needs. Considered on the basis of tourist prospectuses and brochures, the touristic text is a special mass-information and status-oriented institutional discourse. Touristic text is complexly organized, or rather, hybrid, combining the features of advertising, popular science, didactic discourses, and polycode discourse using verbal, iconic, graphic codes. The specificity of this discourse lies in the area of its application - in the field of tourism. The involvement of the addressee in an alternative type of activity accompanying the rest (cognitive, entertaining, health-improving) is facilitated by the argumentative resources of the touristic text.

The clarification of the definition of "tourist discourse" is due to the insufficient degree of study of speech used in situations related to communication in the field of tourism.

For the purpose of a more detailed study, the touristic text was considered in comparison with the advertising one. In terms of its pragmatic orientation (to sell a tourist product) and high information saturation, touristic text approaches advertising discourse. Nevertheless, the features that distinguish the touristic text from the advertising discourse are revealed: the predominance of the informative function in the touristic text, the presentation of detailed information about the real-potential reality, the dominance of the cultural-historical and popular science aspects, as well as universal, national values in the presentation of information.

The functional and semantic types of speech used in touristic text (description, narration, reasoning), forms of presentation of information (monologue, dialogic, polylogical) were analyzed. The combined use of different ways and forms of presentation in the touristic text contributes to the most complete and reasoned transmission of information.

The discursive genres of tourist brochures and brochures are the most common, and, consequently, the most popular printed non-periodical information and reference publications used in the field of tourism. It is noted that travel brochures and brochures are secondary genres. They are characterized by a standard composition (headline - phrase-introduction - main part - conclusion), highly economical presentation of information and the desire for objectivity. Along with the obligatory presentation of the present reality, these genres contain elements of prospection and / or retrospection. In this regard, such editions are both preliminary and subsequent texts.

In addition to general genre characteristics, the features that distinguish tourist brochures from tourist brochures are highlighted. First of all, these distinctive features are explained by the different volume of these publications. Thus, due to their small volume, tourist brochures are characterized by a concise presentation of information (simplified syntax, abbreviated words, selection of the most significant information). Tourist brochures are characterized by redundancy in the presentation of information (numerous repetitions, clarifications, a large number of historical, cultural, geographical and other references, detailed syntactic constructions).

It has been established that when presenting the addresser of the touristic text, linguistic means are used that reflect it, anonymous and collective nature: the pronouns *on* and *nous*, the possessive adjective *our*, marking the non-singularity of the addresser. The sender is characterized by competence, didacticism, popularization, polyphony, helpfulness. Through the dialogical nature characteristic of the addresser, his desire to establish friendly contact, continue communication with the addressee of the touristic text, and influence his further actions is manifested.

The specificity of the touristic text was determined, namely, the presence of such basic functional characteristics of the touristic text as informative, evaluative, motivating, persuasive.

A high degree of informativeness of touristic text is achieved due to the reliability, sufficiency, perceptibility and usefulness of information. Encyclopedic nature ensures the completeness and didactic orientation of information. Popularization gives it an entertaining character and contributes to its better perception. Polycode touristic text has as its goal a highly economical presentation of information and serves to effectively influence the addressee.

Evaluation of touristic text accompanies a positive emotional impact on the addressee, stimulates his further activity. The transfer of evaluativeness is facilitated by affective and qualitative adjectives; superlative adjectives; adverbs that are evaluative in nature or act as an intensifier of a feature; nouns and verbs with positive connotations; accenting means (excretory and restrictive phrases, neologisms, anglicisms, phraseological units, puns); approximators that serve to reduce the categorical nature of the estimate; modal words and expressions; anthropomorphic vocabulary; verbs of opinion; precedent names; tropes (epithets, comparisons, metaphors, personification); semantic-emotive vocabulary, *laisse + infinitive verb constructions*, inversions of sentence members, emotional-expressive syntax.

Models of the texts of tourist prospectuses and brochures receive the appropriate content depending on the value dominant of the touristic text. Taking into account the values of hospitality, stability (security), family, free time, information, freedom, personality, tolerance, respect, mobility, conservatism, traditionalism, education, natural and cultural heritage, the cult of beauty and health, pleasure (pleasure), the addressee of the touristic text creates his appeal to the addressee, and under the influence of the allocated values, the addressee of the touristic text prefers one or another type of recreation.

The motivation of touristic text is determined by the addresser's intention to encourage the addressee to purchase a tour or visit a certain tourism object: categorical motivation (imperativeness), softened motivation, implicit motivation and linguistic means of their implementation are highlighted: verbs in the imperative mood, in the future tense (future simple), in the past the unfinished tense (perfect) and the present tense (present) of the indicative mood; modal words; verbs in the passive form; infinitives in the present tense of the active voice; speech clichés; evaluative and descriptive information; exclamatory and interrogative sentences; headers.

Touristic text is persuasive, because in the process of communication in the field of tourism, an attempt is made to influence the addressee in order to make him decide to go on a trip or visit a particular tourism object. To convince the addressee, different methods of influence are used, where speech is dominant. It has been established that the speech impact on the addressee can be carried out by informing, inciting and evaluating, as well as by an argumentative way of organizing the text, which uses a certain sequence of arguments (for example, the "edge principle") and various connectors (adversarial but; conclusive at last, thus, then; temporary later, after; connective and; comparative otherwise; illustrative indeed, etc.). Rational-logical and persuasive methods of verbal persuasion used in touristic text are considered as argumentation. Argumentation in touristic text has a two-sided character: showing the truth or plausibility of a certain thesis and creating an emotional attitude towards it, which enhances the persuasiveness of this thesis.

5. Touristic text is a strategic process based on the choice of optimal language means. Among the most commonly used tactics and strategies in touristic text, differentiation strategies, value, evaluation strategies, strategies for coordinating the language and worldviews of touristic text participants, strategies for increasing the "readability" of the message are highlighted. The use of the tactics of retrospection and reframing (mental transfer in time and space) significantly distinguishes from other genres of travel brochures and brochures that provide the opportunity for the addressee of the touristic text to move almost instantly in space and time.

The presented study opens, in our opinion, certain prospects for further study of touristic text both in English and other languages. The study outlines ways for a more detailed study of touristic text, in particular, the consideration of iconic, or paralinguistic, means of touristic text as a polycode text.

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СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

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